

DATA FUSION APPROACHES IN SPECTROSCOPIC CHARACTERIZATION AND CLASSIFICATION OF PDO WINE VINEGARS

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Abstract

Spain is one of the major producers of high-quality wine vinegars having three protected designations of origin (a.k.a. PDOs): “Vinagre de Jerez”, “Vinagre de Condado de Huelva” and “Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles”. Their high prices due to their high quality and their high production costs explain the need for developing an adequate quality control technique and the interest in extensive characterization in order to capture the identity of each denomination. In this framework, methodologies based on non-targeted techniques, such as spectroscopies, are becoming popular in food authentication. Thus, for improving vinegar quality assessment, fusion of data blocks obtained from the same samples but different analytical techniques could be a good strategy, since the quantity and quality of sample knowledge could be enhanced providing new insights into the differentiation of vinegars. Therefore, the aim of this manuscript is the development of a multi-platform methodology and a model able to classify the Spanish wine vinegar PDOs. Sixty-five PDO wine vinegars were analyzed by four spectroscopic techniques: Fourier-transform mid-infrared spectroscopy (MIR), near infrared spectroscopy (NIR), multidimensional fluorescence spectroscopy (EEM) and proton nuclear magnetic resonance (¹H-NMR). Two different data fusion strategies were evaluated: Mid-level data fusion with different preprocessing, and Common Component and Specific Weights analysis multiblock method. Exploratory and classification analysis on the data from individual techniques were also performed and compared with data fusion models. The data fusion models improved the classification, providing a more efficient differentiation, than the models based on single methods, and supporting the approach to combine these methods to achieve synergies for an optimized PDO differentiation.

Keywords: wine vinegars, food authentication, spectroscopy, classification, data fusion, P-Comdim.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, there is a growing consumer’s demand for high quality food products. The term “quality” in food is directly related to a known origin and specific chemical composition, adequate and satisfactory physical and sensory properties, as well as meeting safety and health requirements [1,2]. Protected Designation of Origin (PDO) indication is one of the label adopted by the European Community as recognition of some specific food quality attributes. A product with a PDO registration must be produced, processed and prepared in a given geographical area using a recognized know-how [3]. The PDO denomination confers to these products a high added value, consequently there is also an increasing of deceptive practices aiming at counterfeiting them, such as mislabeling of geographical origin, disregarding the production protocol or adulteration of the product. In this respect, assessing the authenticity of traditional food is a complex issue because it has to encompass several aspects going from assessing the compliance to the legal requirements stated in the product label, i.e. controlling the geographical origin and the respect of the traditional protocols, to detecting fraudulent processing practices or adulteration.

Among the PDO products with high demand there are the high-quality vinegars. In particular, in addition to the well-known “Aceto Balsamico Tradizionale di Modena” from Italy [4], Spain is also one of the major producers of high-quality wine vinegars. Thus, three important Spanish wine vinegars have gained the PDO label because of their unique characteristics and traditional production, namely: “Vinagre de Jerez” (also known as “Sherry wine vinegar”), “Vinagre de Condado de Huelva” and the most recently “Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles”. Furthermore, within each PDO, there are different categories according to their time and method of aging (“criaderas and solera” or “añada” systems) in wood barrels as well as the sweetness. The high quality of these wine vinegars is linked to the raw material used (i.e. high quality wines, also protected by the corresponding PDO), the traditional production protocol and method of aging in wooden barrels. Therefore, the high prices of these vinegars, due to their high quality, the long aging time and hence, the high cost of their production, explain the need of proper characterization in order to provide an adequate quality control to defend their identity [4–9].

32 Due to the traditional making procedure, the raw material used and the aging process,
33 these wine vinegars are very complex multi-component mixtures from the chemical
34 point of view, thus different analytical techniques have been applied to obtain an
35 extensive characterization in order to assess their authenticity [6,7,9–11]. Spectroscopic
36 techniques, based on infrared (IR), fluorescence or nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR)
37 spectroscopy, are the most commonly used food fingerprinting techniques in untargeted
38 approach. In particular, these spectroscopic techniques share the advantage of requiring
39 minimal sample preparation, moreover IR is non-destructive and cheap, while NMR may
40 allow quantification of a wide range of compounds. Good results were obtained by
41 spectroscopic analysis of the three Spanish PDO wine vinegars in terms of assessing
42 their aging and sweet categories or characterizing each PDO separately [6,7,12].
43 However, the possibility of discriminating these three wine vinegars PDOs, regardless
44 of the presence of different ageing or sweetness features, within each distinct PDO, has
45 been less considered in the literature [7,9,11].

46 In order to gather more detailed knowledge about the specificity of each PDOs and
47 aiming at improving their quality assessment and differentiation, the combination and
48 fusion of the data acquired by several analytical platforms could be useful [2,13,14].
49 Data fusion methodologies have demonstrated to be a powerful tools for obtaining more
50 reliable authentication models with respect to the results obtained by each technique
51 separately [2,13,15–17]. In fact, the fusion of the different information obtained can
52 enhance the quantity and quality of knowledge about the distinctive features among
53 samples/categories. Moreover, the integration of the different data types into a single
54 model also allows assessing the correlation and the similar/different information content
55 among the different techniques.

56 Data fusion may be accomplished at different levels (i.e. low-, mid- and high-level
57 data fusion), depending on the objective, number and type of data sets to combine
58 [2,18–20]. The low-level fusion is a conceptually simple method: raw data from more
59 than one source are directly fused (concatenated) after preprocessing issues are
60 addressed. This level of data fusion has been widely applied for the authentication and
61 quality control of many food and beverages [2]. The main limitations are a high data
62 volume and the possible predominance of one data source over the others and possible
63 discontinuities regions when spectral data are fused. This is partially overcome by the
64 mid-level fusion, in which a previous extraction of some relevant features from each
65 single data source is performed and then, these features are concatenated into a single

66 array. Moreover, this type of fusion enables an easy interpretation of the results, since
67 the contribution of each individual block can be visualized. The main parameters to take
68 into account are the number of features to retain from each model, the method to be
69 used for data reduction, and the type of scaling to apply, however this last issue is less
70 severe than in low-level data fusion, considering that data reduction has already been
71 applied. Mid-level data fusion has been also applied in authentication and quality
72 control of food and beverages [2,17].

73 On the other hand, other approaches based on multiblock analysis are also suitable in
74 data fusion context, such as the Common Components and Specific Weights Analysis
75 (CCSWA, also referred to as ComDim, which is as well the name of the algorithmic
76 implementation) [21–23], which has been recently revised and extended to the
77 supervised context (P-ComDim) [24], *i.e.* to deal with the case where one of the blocks
78 (Y block) holds responses that are to be predicted on the basis of the information
79 provided by the other blocks. The main purpose of the ComDim algorithm is to provide
80 the common sources of information shared by each data block, *i.e.* the common
81 components, at the same time assigning to each single block a specific weight (or
82 salience) associated to each dimension of the common space [24,25]. This method has
83 been recently applied to the analysis of several food products in order to differentiate
84 *e.g.* an organically or conventional production [26,27], or cheese products obtained by
85 different manufacturing or ripening [28] as well as it has been applied to predict sensory
86 attributes [21].

87 A major general advantage of ComDim approach, compared to the low and mid-level
88 data fusion approaches, is that it provides information about the relation between
89 individual data blocks (*i.e.* common variables) and their contribution to each common
90 component. Thus, ComDim can be applied in order to study the complementarity, and
91 also the differences, of the various spectroscopic techniques. In particular, the study of
92 the saliences (weights of each data block in the common model) could be particularly
93 interesting due to the fact that if a dimension has close saliences for two or more
94 techniques, this may be due to a physical phenomenon that is described in a similar way
95 for both methods. On the other hand, if there is an important difference between the
96 saliences for a given dimension, it could mean that this dimension reveals a
97 phenomenon only visible by one technique and not by the others. This could be used for
98 focusing the selectivity of the spectroscopic techniques studied in this work.

99 Moreover, used in the predictive context, i.e. P-ComDim, we could infer and assess
100 which information in the different data blocks is relevant for the discrimination of the
101 different categories, which is shared and which is peculiar to each of them [24,28,29]

102 Taking this background into consideration, the aim of this work was to perform a
103 multiplatform characterization and develop classification models for the different
104 Spanish wine vinegar PDOs by assessing different data fusion approaches, as well as to
105 study the synergy/complementarity among the techniques considered for that purpose.
106 To this aim, the same wine vinegar samples were measured by four spectroscopic
107 techniques: Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (i.e. mid infrared, MIR), near
108 infrared spectroscopy (NIR), multidimensional fluorescence spectroscopy (EEM) and
109 proton nuclear magnetic resonance ($^1\text{H-NMR}$). These techniques were selected due to
110 the individual efficacy in the characterization of PDO wine vinegars as previously
111 reported [6,7,12] , as well as because they have gained wide acceptance in foods
112 characterization, authenticity and classification purposes [15, 30–34].

113 The main contribution of this study is to comparatively discuss the different data
114 fusion strategies, in term of capability to improve discrimination of the three PDO's
115 vinegars and to highlight the role of each spectroscopic technique. In fact, although they
116 can share some repeated pieces of information, they are mostly complementary.

118 **2. MATERIALS AND METHODS**

119 **2.1. Samples**

120 Sixty-five PDO wine vinegar samples were provided by several local wineries
121 through the Council Regulation of each PDO. Twenty-one samples belonging to the
122 PDO “Vinagre de Condado de Huelva”, twenty-eight to “Vinagre de Jerez” PDO and
123 sixteen to the most recently designed PDO “Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles” were
124 analyzed by the four analytical techniques which are described below. Furthermore,
125 within each PDO, samples from the different commercialized categories (aged and
126 sweet) were included in the analysis. Samples were analyzed in duplicate. More
127 information about the samples is presented in Table 1.

128 **2.2. Instrumental analysis**

129 **2.1.1. Mid-infrared spectroscopy (MIR)**

130 Samples were analyzed, according to the method reported in [6], by using a Bruker
131 Vertex 70 FTIR spectrometer equipped with a DGTS detector (Bruker Optics, Ettlingen,

132 Germany) and a multi-reflection attenuated total reflectance accessory (ATR, six
133 bounces, Specac, Orpington, U.K.). Samples were directly analyzed without sample
134 pre-treatment, recording the spectra at the same temperature (22 ± 0.05 °C) in the region
135 of 4000-600 cm^{-1} (by an average of 50 scans at a resolution of 4 cm^{-1}) and were
136 examined using OPUS version 7.0 (Bruker Optics, Ettlingen, Germany) and
137 manipulated with OMNIC software. The raw MIR spectra are shown in Fig.I.
138 Supplementary Material.

139 **2.1.2. Near-infrared spectroscopy (NIR)**

140 NIR spectra were collected following the method published in [12], by using an ABB
141 Bomen IR spectrometer (Q-interline, X, Denmark), equipped with a 1 mm path length
142 cuvette. Spectral data were collected in the range of 12000–4000 cm^{-1} , resolution of 8
143 cm^{-1} , and 64 scans for both backgrounds and samples. Samples were directly analyzed
144 without sample pre-treatment in a random sequence at room temperature (21 ± 2 °C) by
145 pipetting them into 1 mL shell vial, 40x80 mm transparent (Skandinaviska Genetec AB,
146 Lund, Sweden) before measurement. The spectrometer was interfaced to a computer
147 with GRAMS/AI™ Spectroscopy Software (Thermo Fisher Scientific software) for
148 spectral acquisition and exportation. The raw NIR spectra are shown in Fig.I.
149 Supplementary Material.

150 **2.1.3. Excitation-Emission Multidimensional Fluorescence (EFM)**

151 Wine vinegar samples were directly analyzed without sample pre-treatment an at the
152 same temperature (25.00 ± 0.05 °C) by a Varian Cary-Eclipse fluorescence
153 spectrophotometer (Varian Iberica, Madrid, Spain), equipped with two Czerny-Turner
154 monochromators, and a Xenon discharge lamp pulsed at 80 Hz with a half peak height
155 of ≈ 2 μs , according to the method reported in [7]. Cary-Eclipse software was used for
156 spectral acquisition and exportation. The fluorescence Excitation-Emission Matrices
157 (EEMs) were obtained by varying the excitation wavelength (λ_{ex}) between 250 and 700
158 nm (every 5 nm) and recording the emission spectra (λ_{em}) from 300 to 800 nm (every 2
159 nm), with excitation and emission slits set at 5 nm and the scan rate fixed to 1200 nm
160 min^{-1} . EEMs were preprocessed in order to avoid noisy and non-informative areas by
161 selecting shorter spectral ranges (λ_{ex} from 250 to 680 nm, and λ_{em} from 310 to 800
162 nm). The EEM landscape of a vinegar is shown in Fig.I. Supplementary Material as an
163 example.

164 **2.1.4. ^1H -Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (^1H -NMR)**

165 Samples were prepared by adding 100 μL of 0.16% of 3-(Trimethylsilyl)
166 propionic-2,2,3,3-d₄ acid sodium salt (TMSP-2,2,3,3-d₄) in D₂O (99.97%) dissolution,
167 to 600 μL of each wine vinegar. TMSP was used as both a chemical shift reference
168 ($\delta=0$) and internal standard. ¹H-NMR spectra have been acquired at 300 K of
169 temperature on a Bruker AVIII 700 spectrometer (Bruker Biospin GmbH Rheinstetten,
170 Karlsruhe, Germany) operating at 700.25 MHz. The ¹H-NMR data were acquired using
171 the Bruker spin-echo sequence “cpmgrp.fb” (Carr-Purcell-Meiboom-Gill, Bruker
172 Library) with water presaturation, applied to suppress broad resonance signals. FIDs’
173 have been recorded as the sum of 64 scans of 7.4 s each covering a spectral width of
174 11.0 ppm with 1s between each consecutive scan. Data acquisition was carried out using
175 the "baseopt" Bruker sequence to optimize the baseline after Fourier Transform. The
176 raw ¹H-NMR spectra are shown in Fig.I. Supplementary Material.

177 **2.3. Data analysis**

178 Since four different instrumental fingerprints were recorded for each sample, each
179 one with different data structures, several chemometric algorithms were employed in
180 order to extract and merge the information presents in each data set.

181 The data analysis workflow included: i) building separate models: both exploratory
182 analysis and classification were performed on the data obtained from the individual
183 analytical techniques; ii) in order to take advantage of the multiplatform
184 characterization of the samples, the data of different sources were processed by means
185 of different data fusion (DF) strategies. The objectives were to assess common and
186 specific information pertaining to each analytical platform and obtaining improved
187 classification results. A schematization of the global data analysis flow is presented in
188 Fig.1.

189 *Figure 1 to be inserted about here*

190 **2.3.1. Data sets**

191 In total sixty-five samples were analyzed by each spectroscopic technique. In order
192 to validate the models, the samples were split in a training set of forty-seven samples
193 (fifteen “Vinagre de Condado de Huelva”, twenty “Vinagre de Jerez” and twelve
194 “Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles” PDO samples) and a test set of eighteen samples (six
195 “Vinagre de Condado de Huelva”, eight “Vinagre de Jerez” and four “Vinagre de
196 Montilla-Moriles” PDO samples) using the Duplex algorithm [35]. This algorithm
197 ensures a representative spanning of the whole data domain for both calibration and

198 validation sets, we also checked for a balanced representation of each category in both
199 sets. Moreover, since the number of samples is rather limited, the splitting was repeated
200 five times (always checking by exploratory data analysis, that both sets spanned the
201 whole variability domain and balanced category representation was achieved) hence
202 five classification models were calculated for each analyzed data set (NIR+MIR, NMR,
203 EEM, mid-level Data Fused, P-Comdim raw data and P-Comdim extracted features). In
204 the results the average classification errors are reported.

205 **2.3.2. Decomposition methods**

206 As summarized in Fig. 1, different decomposition methods were applied, according
207 to the type of dataset, for exploratory data analysis as well as for data reduction to
208 obtain the features which were then used for the data fusion models, *i.e.* mid-level DF
209 and features-based P-ComDim.

210 MIR and NIR individual data sets, as detailed in Section 2.3.5.1, were concatenated
211 at low-level DF and the obtained dataset was compressed by principal component
212 analysis (PCA).

213 The EEM data array, after Rayleigh and Raman scattering correction [7], was
214 decomposed by PARAllel FACTor analysis (PARAFAC) [36,37] in order to extract the
215 relevant features (fluorophores).

216 Finally, for ¹H-NMR dataset, after proper alignment and baseline correction,
217 multivariate curve resolution (MCR) [38,39] was used to resolve the chemical
218 components. The peak areas of the resolved components were then used as features.

219 PARAFAC and MCR decomposition methods have been widely described in the
220 literature. Applied constrains and preprocessing details for each data block are reported
221 in Section 2.3.4.

222 **2.3.3. Classification Analysis.**

223 Partial least squares-discriminant analysis (PLS-DA) is a classification technique
224 based on partial least squares (PLS) algorithm with a so-called dummy matrix reporting
225 class membership as Y block [40]. In our study, three different Spanish PDO were
226 considered, therefore, the size of the Y dummy matrix was $n^{\circ} \text{ samples} \times 3$ (one column
227 for each one of the classes) and codification was 1/0 (belonging/not belonging to the
228 category).

229 In the case of EEM data set, which is a three-way array, N-way Partial least squares-
230 discriminant analysis (NPLS-DA) [41] based on multilinear PLS (NPLS) [42] has been
231 used and codification of the Y block is the same as for PLS-DA.

232 In both cases, classification was achieved by applying linear discriminant
233 analysis (LDA) on the X-scores calculated by PLS-DA/NPLS-DA [43]. The minimum
234 classification error rate in cross-validation (venetian blind, seven splits) was used to
235 assess the number of latent variables, i.e. components of the PLS-DA/NPLS-DA
236 models.

237 **2.3.4. Preprocessing and analysis of individual data blocks**

238 **2.3.4.1. MIR and NIR datasets**

239 Concerning the MIR data, as is described in our previous work [6], no
240 preprocessing was needed and the raw spectra were just mean centered. Moreover, only
241 the region between 1500 and 900 cm^{-1} was included in the analysis [6] in order to
242 discard the uninformative variables with excessive noise.

243 With regards to NIR data, different preprocessing methods were evaluated prior
244 to data analysis as was contemplated in a previous work [12] The best pre-processing
245 approach resulted to be smoothing (Savitzky-Golay filter, 7 points window and second
246 order polynomial degree) to reduce random noise, followed by standard normal variate
247 (SNV) [44] to correct additive scattering. In addition, the spectra were always mean
248 centered prior to any analysis. As mentioned before, based on previous expertise or
249 literature [12,45,46], two segments of the spectrum were removed from the whole
250 acquired wavenumber range: the first one (4000-5430 cm^{-1}) because of low signal/noise
251 ratio and the second one due to the strong combination band of O-H from water (7200-
252 6400 cm^{-1}).

253 **2.3.4.2. EEM dataset**

254 EEM data were preprocessed in order to avoid noisy and non-informative areas
255 by selecting shorter spectral ranges, according to the preprocessing steps described in
256 [7]. Thus, the emission over 680 nm and the excitation below 310 nm were cut. Then,
257 EEM data were corrected for Rayleigh and Raman scattering [47], removing and
258 replacing the scattering areas with interpolated values [47]. After this correction, EEM
259 data was decomposed by PARAFAC [37]. A model based on five factors, constrained
260 for non-negativity in all modes (both concentration and spectral profiles), was built. The
261 proper number of factors was determined by taking into account the CORE
262 CONSistency DIAGnostic test (COR- CONDIA) [48], the explained variance and the
263 visual inspection of the recovered spectral profiles and residuals. The PARAFAC scores
264 (first mode loadings) for these factors were used as features to build the mid-level fused
265 dataset.

266 **2.3.4.3. ¹H-NMR dataset**

267 Prior to data analysis, several preprocessing steps were applied to NMR spectra. The
268 regions below 0.84 ppm and over 9.8 ppm were discarded because they were
269 uninformative. Also the region between 4.75 and 5 ppm was removed since it contained
270 the residual water signal not completely removed by the instrumental presaturation step.
271 To correct for the inhomogeneous pH-dependent chemical shifts, all spectra were
272 aligned by means of icoshift [49] whereas weighted least squares (WLS) [50] was used
273 for baseline correction.

274 Then, MCR was applied. The whole ¹H-NMR data was divided into 52 intervals of
275 different size in order to avoid splitting the single NMR signals. This task was
276 performed manually by making use of the previous knowledge of NMR chemical shifts
277 of the main wine and vinegar compounds [33,51,52]. These intervals are shown in Fig.
278 II. Supplementary Material. The MCR settings were the same for each interval: the
279 number of components was determined by inspection of PCA explained variance and
280 SIMPLISMA [53] was used to obtain the initial estimation of the pure spectral profile.
281 The peak areas of the resolved concentration profiles (chemical components) within
282 each interval were calculated by integration and used as features for the subsequent
283 fused data set.

284 In order to achieve a tentative assignment of the ¹H-NMR resolved components, both
285 Chenomx NMR Suite 7.0 (Chenomx, Edmonton, Canada), as well as assignments
286 reported in literature [33,51,52,54,55] were used. Sixty-two components were resolved
287 and integrated; thirty-five of these were tentatively assigned. Those components that
288 were not possible to assign, are named as “X” plus a number. The fact that several
289 regions of the NMR spectra could not be associated to a single signal is due to the many
290 overlapped multiplets present, which impair certain identification. On the other hand,
291 they could be attributed to overall contribution of a class of compounds, such as sugars
292 (between 3-4 ppm). In our case, in this region, only glucose and fructose could be
293 separately assessed.

294 **2.3.5. Data fusion strategies**

295 **2.3.5.1. Low-level fusion of MIR and NIR data**

296 In the low-level strategy, fusion occurs by concatenating the original data matrices,
297 opportunely pretreated and then analyzing the resulting array as a single data block.

298 The MIR and NIR spectra were single preprocessed as described in Sections 2.3.4.1.
299 Then, the matrices describing the individual blocks were concatenated to obtain a single
300 one, having as many rows as samples analyzed and as many columns as spectral
301 wavelengths selected for each data set. This new matrix was additionally normalized in
302 order to compensate for the different measuring scales and variability of each technique
303 in order to prevent one block from being dominant in the subsequent data analysis [2].
304 Thus, block-scaling, to equalize variance, and mean centering were applied. Doing so,
305 each block presented variance equal to one, but the ratio of the variance between any
306 two variables inside a single block was preserved.

307 After preprocessing, a PCA model based on 8 principal components, accordingly to
308 Scree plot and explaining 99.87% of total variance, was selected and the extracted score
309 vectors were used as MIR/NIR features to build the fused dataset.

310 A possible alternative approach consists of applying PCA to the separate MIR and
311 NIR spectral data and then using the extracted features (distinct set of PCs) in mid-level
312 DF; this approach was also considered and gave very similar results.

313 **2.3.5.2. Mid-level data fusion**

314 In the mid-level strategy, fusion occurs at the level of features extracted from the
315 different data blocks. In this study, as Fig.1 shows, the final fused array was assembled
316 using the 8 PCA scores from MIR and NIR, the 5 factors from the PARAFAC model of
317 EEM data, and the peak areas of the 62 resolved components by MCR of ¹H-NMR data.

318 As in the case of low-level fusion, since the extracted features in mid-level data
319 fusion can have different numerical characteristics, scaling of the fused matrix [2,15,17]
320 was performed. Different preprocessing tools were assessed: autoscaling and block-
321 autoscaling (each data set corresponding to an analytical technique was considered as a
322 block). In block-autoscaling, each variable is first scaled to unit variance (autoscaling),
323 and then each block is scaled to equal variance. As a result, each block presented unit
324 variance and each variable inside a block had its variance equal to $1/n_{\text{block}}$, where n_{block}
325 is the number of variables in a given block.

326 **2.3.5.3. P-ComDim**

327 The recently proposed P-ComDim (*i.e.*, Predictive ComDim) method [24], which is
328 the extension of the multiblock method ComDim to the supervised context, has also
329 been evaluated as a different data fusion strategy. For details on P-ComDim algorithm
330 the reader is referred to literature [24,25]. Briefly we recall the main feature of the
331 method. P-ComDim can be applied to any number of data blocks, of which the

332 dependent one is denoted by \mathbf{Y} and the independent ones by \mathbf{X}_k . The first step in P-
 333 ComDim algorithm is calculating the kernel matrices:

$$334 \quad \mathbf{S}_k = \mathbf{X}_k \mathbf{X}_k^T \mathbf{Y} \mathbf{Y}^T \quad (1)$$

335 Then a “common singular value decomposition” is conducted, by minimizing the
 336 criterion:

$$337 \quad \sum_{k=1}^K \|\mathbf{S}_k - \lambda_k \mathbf{t} \mathbf{t}^T\|^2 \quad (2)$$

338 obtaining a first common component for the \mathbf{X} -blocks, i.e. \mathbf{t}_1 , as well as a component
 339 in \mathbf{Y} -space, i.e. \mathbf{u}_1 . Further components are then calculated sequentially after deflation
 340 of both \mathbf{X} -blocks and \mathbf{Y} -block. As for standard ComDim, each single \mathbf{X} -block (\mathbf{X}_k)
 341 contributes to a common component according to its salience, λ_k [29]. It is also possible
 342 to associate to each block \mathbf{X}_k a local component by calculating:

$$343 \quad \mathbf{t}^{(k)} = \mathbf{X}_k \mathbf{X}_k^T \mathbf{t} \quad (3)$$

344 i.e. eq. (3) maps \mathbf{t} into a latent variable which lies in the space spanned by the
 345 variables in \mathbf{X}_k . This latent variable $\mathbf{t}^{(k)}$ is used to recover and interpret the specific
 346 contribution of the \mathbf{X}_k -block variables to the global latent variable \mathbf{t} .

347 To accomplish classification, the \mathbf{Y} -block holds the class membership information,
 348 as described in section 2.3.3. and a classification model can be built by applying PLS-
 349 DA to the \mathbf{u} -scores obtained by P-ComDim. Prediction is accomplished by first
 350 estimating, in prediction, the \mathbf{u} -scores for the test samples (\mathbf{u} -test) in P-ComDim, then
 351 using the \mathbf{u} -test in PLS-DA as prediction set. In our case, the number of PLS-DA
 352 components was estimated according to minimum classification error in CV using the
 353 same splits and classification rule as described in Section 2.3.3. Also the subdivision in
 354 training and test sets was the same as described in Section 2.3.1.

355 Moreover, in P-ComDim methodology, two different strategies were performed and
 356 compared. In the first, ComDim was developed using the raw spectra of MIR, NIR,
 357 EEM and $^1\text{H-NMR}$ as \mathbf{X} -blocks after applying the same spectral preprocessing as
 358 described in Section 2.3.4. MIR and NIR data were mean centered, the $^1\text{H-NMR}$ data
 359 was block-scaled by dividing the spectra into six regions (0.84-1.15, 1.15-1.5, 1.5-2.0,
 360 2.0-2.25, 2.25-3.2, 3.2-9.8 ppm) to compensate for major differences in spectral region
 361 signal intensities and the EEM data array of dimensions I -samples \times J -excitation \times L -
 362 emission wavelengths, was unfolded to a matrix of dimensions $I \times JL$.

363 In the second, the extracted features of each data block (PCA scores from MIR/NIR,
364 MCR peaks areas of resolved components, and PARAFAC factors) were used as X -
365 blocks.

366 Both in the first and second cases, each data table X_k was normalized in order to
367 obtain the data tables having the same inertia as usually done in ComDim algorithm
368 [56].

369 The interpretation of each model and comparison of two approaches (i.e. with raw
370 spectra and with the features) was performed by studying the saliences, global and local
371 scores/loadings [28,29], and the classification performance.

372 **2.3.6. Software**

373 Preprocessing, PARAFAC, PCA, PLS-DA and NPLS-DA models were calculated by
374 using routines of PLS Toolbox 6.5 (Eigenvector Research Inc., WA, USA) working
375 under MATLAB environment v.2016a (Mathworks, MA, USA). LDA was calculated
376 by using the Statistics and Machine Learning Toolbox v. 10.1. Multivariate curve
377 resolution was carried out by using the MCR-ALS GUI (<http://www.mcrals.info>) and a
378 MATLAB routine implemented to automatically work on spectral intervals, courtesy
379 from Prof. R. Bro's group. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ data acquisition, Fourier transformation and
380 spectral preprocessing were carried out using Bruker TopSpin 3.0 and Chenomx NMR
381 Suite 7.0 (Chenomx, Edmonton, Canada) was used to obtain a tentative assignment of
382 the $^1\text{H-NMR}$ resolved components.

383 P-ComDim models were obtained by using routines developed by Prof. D. Rutledge
384 and the SAISIR package for MATLAB [57,58].

386 **3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

387 This section is articulated in three main parts. In the first one, the description of
388 exploratory analysis results for the individual data sets, as well as the feature extraction
389 step (Sections 3.1), and the respective classification models (Section 3.2) are reported.
390 In the second part (Section 3.3), the fused dataset is considered and the application of
391 the mid-level approach is described in detail. The third part (Section 3.4) presents the
392 results obtained by P-ComDim in order to study the complementarity of the techniques.

393 **3.1. Exploratory analysis of individual data matrices**

394 MIR and NIR data were preprocessed and fused as described in Section 2.3.5.1,
395 the results of exploratory PCA analysis (8 PCs, accounting for 99.8% of the total
396 variance) are reported in Figure III of the Supplementary Material. The three categories

397 strongly overlap and a partial trend of separation was only observed on the scores plot
398 of the PC1, PC3 and PC8 (Fig. III.A), inspecting the corresponding loading plots (Fig.
399 III.B) it can be observed that PC1 mainly distinguishes the sweet Pedro Ximenez sub-
400 category which is present in both “Vinagre de Jerez” and “Vinagre de Montilla-
401 Moriles” PDOs (the contributing spectral regions have been associated with the
402 presence of grape sugars, furfural and Maillard compounds [6,12,46,59]). “Vinagre de
403 Montilla-Moriles” PDO samples are partially separated from “Vinagre de Jerez” PDO
404 along PC3 to which are contributing peaks (Fig. III.B) that have been assigned to
405 chemical compounds that change during aging, e.g. some alcohol, aldehydes, esters,
406 ethers and acids [6, 12,46,60].

407 The EEM data array was preprocessed and decomposed by PARAFAC as described
408 in Section 2.3.4.2 obtaining a five factors model (explained variance 99%), which is in
409 good agreement with the three individual PARAFAC models obtained in our previous
410 work [7] for each one of the three PDOs. Fig. 2.A and B includes the PARAFAC
411 loadings for mode 2 and 3 (excitation and emission spectra) of the extracted factors. The
412 excitation and emission maxima of these extracted factors, as well as their possible
413 matching fluorophores according to the literature and our previous knowledge [7,62],
414 are listed in Table 2.

415 *Figure 3 to be inserted about here*

416 Fig. 3.C shows the average value of the scores (first mode loadings) for samples
417 belonging to each PDO vs. the number of PARAFAC factors. The “Vinagre de
418 Montilla-Moriles” PDO presents higher values on the first and the second factors, with
419 respect to the other two PDOs. Hence, higher presence of components coming from raw
420 materials, which is indicative of less aging, as well as more amount of caramel and 5-
421 Hydroxymethylfurfural (Table 2). However, it is difficult to highlight a clear separation
422 of samples belonging to each class in any of the scatter plots of PARAFAC scores (plots
423 not shown for sake of brevity).

424
425 The NMR data set built with the integrated areas of the sixty-two resolved
426 components (Table 3), obtained by MCR analysis of the ¹H-NMR spectra (as is detailed
427 in Section 2.3.3.4) was preprocessed by autoscaling prior to PCA analysis (six
428 components, explained variance 90.3%). The score and loading plots of the PCs that
429 better highlighted the separation between the three PDOs are shown on Figure IV
430 Supplementary Material. Also in this case a strong overlap is present and only a partial

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431 separation trend of “Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles” PDO samples from “Vinagre de
432 Condado de Huelva” can be observed. The loadings plot (Fig. IVB) highlight, similar to
433 MIR-NIR PCA results, that: i) the first component distinguishes the Pedro Ximenez
434 sweet samples from the rest (contribution from the sugar spectral region, compounds
435 labeled from 34 to 43 in Table 3) and ii) samples from “Vinagre de Condado de
436 Huelva” PDO seem to have higher amount of acetic acid (feature named 18 in Table 3)
437 and ethanol (features 8 and 37, Table 3 with respect to the other two PDOs (separation
438 on PC5).

439

440 **3.2. Classification results of individual datasets.**

441 In a first stage, separate classification models (PLS-DA for MIR+NIR and ¹H-NMR
442 data sets and NPLS-DA as described in previous sections for EEM data) were built on
443 the data coming from the different instrumental techniques. The distinct datasets were
444 split in the same training and test sets of 47 and 19 samples as described in Section 2.3.

445 The classification results obtained by the application of PLS-DA and NPLS-DA on
446 each separate data set, according to the classification criterion described in Section
447 2.3.3, are reported in Table 4, which reports for each spectroscopic technique the data
448 preprocessing, the model dimensionality (assessed by cross-validation) and the
449 classification performance. PLS-DA was built on the PCA scores (8 PCs) for the MIR-
450 NIR data set, and on the sixty-two peak areas of MCR resolved components for the
451 NMR data set, respectively. While for EEM data set, NPLS-DA was directly built on
452 the spectral data array (samples x excitation wavelengths x emission wavelengths).

453 The classification results, in calibration, are promising for ¹H-NMR models (correct
454 classification rates higher than 90% for all categories). The model dimensionality, i.e. 7
455 components, is lower with respect to MIR+NIR, i.e. 10, and EEM, i.e. 12, probably
456 because in this case peak areas of resolved spectral components are used instead of the
457 spectroscopic signal itself. In contrast, the models built on MIR+NIR data and EEM
458 show quite good classification rates, only for one of the category, namely “Condado”
459 and “Jerez” for MIR+NIR and EEM, respectively. These results agree with what
460 already observed in our previous studies [6,7], in which it was shown that these
461 techniques had a better ability to distinguish between categories (aging and sweet) than
462 among the different PDOs.

463 It can also be observed, that NPLS-DA requires an higher number of latent variables,
464 with respect to the number of PARAFAC factors obtained for EEM data (i.e. five), this

465 could be explained by the fact that NPLS-DA (as PLS usually does) modulates the main
466 fluorophores present in the matrix as well as the environment effects and the
467 interferences.

468 On the other hand, the predictive capability (external validation) was almost similar
469 for all the techniques. In general, the results could be considered fairly good, taking into
470 account that, due to the limited number of test samples, for example, in the case of ¹H-
471 NMR, 75% correct prediction rates for the classes “Vinagre de Jerez” and “Vinagre de
472 Montilla-Moriles” PDO correspond to 2 and 1 misclassified samples, respectively. In all
473 the prediction models, the same sample of “Vinagre de Jerez” PDO sample was
474 misclassified; also one sample of “Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles” PDO was always
475 misclassified.

476 Furthermore, it can be observed that prediction rates were higher for “Vinagre de
477 Condado de Huelva” (MIR-NIR and ¹H-NMR models) and “Vinagre de Jerez” (EEM
478 model) with respect to “Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles”. This fact could be mainly
479 explained by the relative new recognition of this PDO (included in the European
480 Register of Protected Geographical Indications and Protected Designation (PGI) in
481 2015), in comparison with the other two PDOs, “Vinagre de Condado de Huelva” and
482 “Vinagre de Jerez” PDOs, and specially the last one that was the first wine vinegar PDO
483 of Spain [3]. Furthermore, this is in agreement with our previous studies [7].

484 To summarize, even though the results are quite promising, the quality of each model
485 was not enough good for the characterization and classification purpose and it varied
486 significantly from one technique to another.

487 **3.3. Mid-level data fusion**

488 The results described in Sections 3.1.4 showed that classification models built on
489 each of the individual data matrices are not accurate enough, indicating that a single
490 instrumental fingerprint is not completely able to correctly predict the high-complex
491 samples under study. For this reason, the possibility of combining the information from
492 the different instruments by means of mid-level data fusion strategy was investigated.

493 The features obtained from the decomposition of the single data blocks (i.e. the eight
494 MIR+NIR PCA scores, the five factors EEM PARAFAC scores and the peak areas of
495 the sixty-two resolved ¹H-NMR MCR components) were merged in a unique block as
496 described in Section 2.3.4 (Fig. 1). Since scaling is a critical issue both block-
497 autoscaling and autoscaling (Section 2.3.4.) were compared.

498 Explorative PCA models were built with the fused data preprocessed by both
499 scaling's methods and results shown in Fig. 3. The autoscaled data (Fig. 3.A) showed a
500 similar clustering of the three PDOs as the one observed in the score plot of ¹H-NMR
501 PCA reported in Fig. IV.A Supplementary Material. In particular, PC1 distinguish the
502 samples belonging to the sweet category at positive values of PC1. "Vinagre de
503 Montilla-Moriles" PDO showed positive scores values on PC5, whereas "Vinagre de
504 Condado de Huelva" PDO samples showed negative scores values for this component
505 and samples of "Vinagre de Jerez" PDO are placed again in the middle. Fig. 3.B shows
506 the loading plot of the same principal components, in which the contribution of several
507 of the features, both from ¹H-NMR and MIR-NIR was observed. PC5, PC2 and PC8
508 from MIR-NIR PCA, as well as several of the NMR features, seem to be the main
509 responsible features for the improvement in the separation of "Vinagre de Condado de
510 Huelva" and "Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles" samples. In fact, they have high negative
511 loadings values on the fifth component of the PCA on fused data, while at positive
512 loadings values there are PC4 and PC6 from MIR-NIR PCA and F1-F3 from
513 PARAFAC. PC1 from MIR-NIR PCA seems of relevance in the Pedro Ximenez
514 samples separation from the rest, since its high positive loadings on the first component
515 of the PCA on fused data.

516 *Figure 3 to be inserted about here*

517 Even if few minor differences were noticed with respect to ¹H-NMR data analysis,
518 some improvements in the separation of PDOs occurred. The similarity between the
519 fused autoscaled data and the ¹H-NMR data block is explained by the fact that using
520 autoscaling as merging strategy, a higher importance is given to the block of variables
521 more numerous, hence, the ¹H-NMR data.

522 Regarding the block-autoscaling PCA results (Fig. 3B), the principal components
523 that better shows a separation were PC1, PC2 and PC5. In this scores plot, the
524 separation of PDOs seems to be worse than with autoscaling procedure. Thus, a higher
525 overlapping between "Vinagre de Jerez" and "Vinagre de Condado de Huelva" samples
526 was observed. In spite of this, "Vinagre de Jerez" PDO seems to be mainly placed in the
527 negative side of PC1 while "Vinagre de Condado de Huelva" in the positive side of PC1
528 and PC5, and "Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles" PDO in the positive side of PC2. The
529 loadings plot (Fig. 3.D) shows in this particular scaling procedure that ¹H-NMR
530 components had lower relevance and the MIR-NIR and EEM variables became more
531 influential. Thus, PC3 (MIR-NIR) and F5 (EEM) showed the most negative

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532 contribution of PC1, while F4, F1 and PC1 the most positive, as well as PC2 and PC8 of
533 MIR-NIR data had the most positive values of PC5, relevant for the separation of
534 “Vinagre de Condado de Huelva” PDO.

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535 Then, PLS-DA models were built using six and seven latent variables for autoscaling
536 and block-autoscaling procedures, respectively (chosen accordingly to minimum cross
537 validation classification errors). The results obtained are reported in Table 5. They
538 confirmed the improvement with respect to the classification models obtained for the
539 separate data blocks. In fact, 100% of correct classification was obtained for the
540 predicted samples (test set) of all the PDOs, as well as 100% of “Vinagre de Condado
541 de Huelva” PDO samples were correctly classified in both fit and the prediction. The
542 two scaling procedures give very similar PLS-DA classification rates, only the number
543 of latent variables were different.

544 In order to identify the most effective variables in discriminating the PDO samples,
545 the values of the PLS-DA regression vectors and the variable importance in projection
546 (VIP) index were studied; for interpretative purposes all the predictors having a $VIP > 1$
547 are considered to be relevant [69]. Despite the different scaling procedure, the variables
548 with VIP higher than one quite matched in both PLS-DA models and are reported in
549 Table 6 together with the sign of the corresponding regression coefficients.
550 Accordingly, the most relevant variables for the discrimination of the “Vinagre de
551 Condado de Huelva” PDO were mainly MIR-NIR PC2, PC3, PC5 and PC8 previously
552 described as the spectral regions related to the presence of acetic acid and ethanol
553 (~ 1410 and ~ 1290 cm^{-1} and 1045 cm^{-1} in MIR spectra) as well as alcohol compounds,
554 aldehydes, and some esters and ethers that matched with PC3 loadings. Other important
555 variables were EFM F1 and F4 that matched with the presence of phenolic compounds
556 and NMR7, NMR11, NMR16, NMR18 and NMR27 that were interpreted as
557 isopropanol, acetic acid, acetoin and some other compounds such as 6-acetylglucose,
558 beta-alanine and succinates.

559 Regarding “Vinagre de Jerez” PDO, this PDO was described mostly by the variables
560 PC3 and PC8 of MIR-NIR PCA, related to alcohol compounds, aldehydes, esters, ethers
561 and acids and commonly presented in grapes, wine and vinegar; EEM F5 related to
562 grape sugars, furfural and Maillard compounds more presented the Pedro Ximenez
563 category included in this PDO, together with F1 and F4 again; and NMR16, NMR26
564 and NMR59 identified as 6-acetylglucose, aminoacids as malate, glutarate or n-
565 acetylglutamate and formic acid, respectively.

566 Finally, the variables that seems to give a relevant contribution for the classification
567 of “Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles” PDO were mainly: MIR-NIR PC5 and PC8 whose
568 loadings mainly showed a peak at 1045 cm⁻¹ and PC1 again related to the Pedro
569 Ximenez samples of this PDO; EFM F1 and F5, which brings mainly the information of
570 the compounds commonly presented in grapes and wine such as cumarins, tannins,
571 phenols, flavonols, and moreover, compounds related to the sweet category such as
572 HMF and sugars also related to the NMR most relevant variables according to the VIPs
573 (i.e. compounds from NMR32 to NMR52). These results agree with those obtained in
574 the loadings plot of the PCA model previously described (Fig. 3).

575 3.4. P-ComDim.

576 P-ComDim was carried out with the raw spectral data (Fig. 4a and Fig. 5a) and the
577 data of the extracted features (Fig. 4b and Fig. 5b) in order to study the best approach
578 that show the complementarity of the techniques and therefore also their differences.
579 Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 shows the saliences and the global loadings obtained [28,70] for each
580 technique, respectively.

581 *Figure 4 to be inserted about here*

582 In Fig. 4 on the top is shown the percentage of variance extracted by each common
583 component (graph on top left), the sum of saliences of all data tables for each common
584 component (graph on top middle) and the sum of saliences for each data table over all
585 the calculated common components (graph on top right). Taking into account the
586 normalization of the single data table, the sum of saliences in the latter plot can be at
587 maximum equal to 1, when no residual variance is left, for that data table after
588 extracting the common components. In the bottom part of Fig. 4 are shown the saliences
589 of each data table on each common component. The sum of the saliences reported on
590 top of each graph corresponds to the values reported on the top middle graph. The first
591 two components explain most of the data variance but taking into account eight
592 components allows describing all data tables.

593 The analysis of salience for the raw spectral data (Fig. 4.A) show that MIR and NIR
594 share mainly one common component, i.e. CC1, while EEM and ¹H-NMR data seem to
595 capture most distinctive information, contributing to different components, namely CC2
596 for EEM and CC3, CC4, CC5 and CC6 for ¹H-NMR. Despite with lower weights, CC8
597 is common to MIR, NIR and ¹H-NMR data blocks and CC7 to all of them. Regarding
598 the loadings vectors associated to each block (Fig. 5.A), CC1 seemed to be related to

599 the Pedro Ximenez category due to the intense band showed in MIR and NIR loadings
600 plot (between 1000-1150 cm⁻¹ and 5200 and 6500 cm⁻¹, respectively) and in ¹H-NMR
601 data point to a higher intensity in the sugar region of the spectra (from 3.22-4.12 ppm);
602 CC2, considering the excitation and emission wavelengths of the EEM reshaped
603 landscapes, resemble the first PARAFAC factor (Fig. 2), while CC3 was related to the
604 first region of the ¹H-NMR spectra were acids (e.g. acetic acid), alcohols (e.g. ethanol)
605 and some esters (isobutyrate) appear. Finally, CC7 seemed to be associated to the
606 presence of acetic acid and ethanol that could be observed by NIR, MIR and ¹H-NMR
607 techniques and, as far as EEM loadings are concerned, the profile resembles those of the
608 fourth PARAFAC factor which was associated to phenols compounds.

609 *Figure 5 to be inserted about here*

610 In the case of P-ComDim model, obtained with the extracted features of each data
611 block (Fig. 4.B), EEM (data table numbered as 2 in the figure) has again little in
612 common with the other data tables and mainly contribute to CC1 and CC4, which by
613 inspection of loadings are related to the first four PARAFAC factors (CC1) and second,
614 third and fifth factors (CC3), respectively. ¹H-NMR data contribute mainly to CC5 and
615 CC6 together with MIR and NIR data, i.e. these global components are shared by these
616 data tables and, hence, should reflect the samples trends common to ¹H-NMR and MIR-
617 NIR. CC2 is mainly contributing the NMR data table and the respective loadings (Fig.
618 5B) show high influence of the first region of the ¹H-NMR spectra (alcohols and acids).
619 CC3, CC7 and CC8 are mainly contributing the MIR-NIR data table, in particular,
620 according to the loadings plot (Fig. 5B), the PC6 and PC8 scores of PCA decomposition
621 of NIR-MIR spectra.

622 Fig. 6 illustrates the global scores scatter plot obtained by P-ComDim analysis (the
623 bottom plot in Fig. 6A and the bottom right one in Fig. 6B). In comparison to PCA
624 analysis of individual spectral data sets (Fig. II and Fig. IV Supplementary Material),
625 ComDim clearly shows an increased separation trend according to the PDO, even
626 though this separation was slightly worse than in the PCA obtained on the mid-level
627 fused data (Fig. 3). These results are consistent with the fact that the global scores
628 scatter plot of P-ComDim obtained on the extracted features data tables, i.e.
629 corresponding to the data used for the mid-level data fusion, show a better separation
630 among PDOs than the ComDim performed on the raw spectral data. These results could
631 be better observed by the scores plot of the PLS-DA models obtained for each approach

632 (Fig. 6). Thus, this latter figure showed that more overlapping occurs when PLS-DA is
633 carried out with raw data than by using the extracted features of each data set (i.e. six
634 samples were not correctly predicted by the raw data model with respect to the two
635 samples wrongly predicted by the model with extracted features). Nonetheless, one
636 advantage of performing P-ComDim directly on the raw spectra is the interpretation of
637 the spectral regions contribution by visualization of the corresponding local loadings.

638 *Figure 6 to be inserted about here*

639 The classification results expressed as percentage of corrected classified by means of
640 PLS-DA model carried out with P-ComDim results are reported in Table 5 together
641 with the classification results obtained by the mid-level data fusion models. Looking at
642 the table it can be noticed once more that the results obtained by the PLSDA performed
643 on the P-ComDim scores from the extracted features were better than the PLS-DA
644 results obtained by each data set individually studied, only comparable to the ¹H-NMR
645 results, as well as they were better than the P-ComDim classification model developed
646 with raw data. However, in spite the promising classification rates obtained by the P-
647 ComDim with the extracted features, the classification results were inferior to the
648 results obtained by Mid-level data fusion.

649 **4. CONCLUSIONS**

650 This study demonstrates the potential of the combination of four spectroscopic
651 analytical methods (MIR, NIR, EFM and ¹H-NMR) when they were combined. The
652 application of data fusion methods improved the characterization and authentication of
653 PDO wine vinegars, providing a more efficient differentiation than the models based on
654 single methods. The obtained results support the approach of combining these methods
655 to achieve synergies for an optimized differentiation of the PDO of wine vinegars. With
656 regard to single analytical methods, especially the classification results of ¹H-NMR
657 models were promising. On the other hand, the application of P-ComDim method was
658 useful for describing, in a simple and synthetic manner, the overall spectral information
659 collected and reveal the complementarity and differences of the spectroscopic
660 techniques, assessing the importance of each technique to each of the common
661 variables. However, for a PDO classification objective, the results of the present work
662 showed that Mid-level data fusion can be the better option in comparison to the
663 classification models obtained by P-ComDim. In spite of this fact, this study presents

664 promising results related to the development of efficient classification models by P-
665 ComDim carried out with the extracted features of spectroscopic data.

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FIGURE CAPTIONS

1
2 Fig. 1. Graphical representation of the data sets, data analysis flow and data fusion
3 process.
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6 Fig. 2. Emission and Excitation spectra (PARAFAC loadings) of the main fluorophores
7 present in the PDO wine vinegars (A and B). Mean PARAFAC scores of each PDO for
8 the five resolved components (C). The acronyms for the different vinegar PDOs are
9 defined in Table 1.
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14 Fig. 3. 3-D plot of PCA scores and loadings obtained for both data fusion strategies
15 (with autoscaling and block-autoscaling preprocessing). The acronyms for the different
16 vinegar PDOs are defined in Table 1.
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20 Fig. 4. Graph of saliencies and sum of saliencies obtained by the P-ComDim method
21 developed with the raw data (A) and with the extracted features (B).
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25 Fig. 5. Global loadings for each data block and global scores plot obtained by P-
26 ComDim method carried out by using the raw spectral data of MIR, NIR, $^1\text{H-NMR}$ and
27 EFM scores (A) and the data of extracted features obtained by MIR-NIR PCA, EFM
28 PARAFAC and $^1\text{H-NMR}$ MCR compounds (B).
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33 Fig. 6. Scores for the first two latent variables of the PLS-DA classification model
34 obtained by P-ComDim with the raw data (A) and extracted features (B). The acronyms
35 for the different vinegar PDOs are defined in Table 1. Test samples are represented by
36 filled symbols. The labels (letter indicate the category predicted by the model) highlight
37 misclassified samples.
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Table 1**Table 1. Samples included in the study.**

PDO	Category	Ageing	n
“Vinagre de Jerez” (J)	Crianza	≥6 months	11
	Reserva	≥2 years	13
	Pedro Ximenez	-	4
	Total		28
“Vinagre de Condado de Huelva” (C)	Without ageing	0 months	5
	Solera	≥6 months	5
	Reserva	≥2 years	8
	Añada	≥3 years (static system)	3
	Total		21
“Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles” (M)	Crianza	≥6 months	8
	Reserva	≥2 years	3
	Pedro Ximenez	-	5
	Total		16

Table 2

Table 2. Emission and Excitation maxima of the 5 factor PARAFAC model and their possible matching fluorophores.

	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
Ex/Em (nm)	380/450	425/520	475/565	380/425	550/630
Fluorophores	Cumarins, tannins, phenols, flavonols from wine	5-Hydroxymethylfurfural caramel	Vitamin B2 and its principal forms	Phenolic compounds, Maillard products, oxidation products	Unknown related to Pedro Ximenez vinegars

Table 3

Table 3. MCR resolved, integrated and interpreted components for ¹H-NMR data.

RT	Type*	Code	Interpretation
0.86-0.9	t	NMR1	2-Hydroxy-3-methylvalerate
0.9-0.97	d + m	NMR2	X1
0.98-1.02	t+q	NMR3	X3
	-	NMR4	X4
1.03-1.06	d	NMR5	Isobutyrate
1.06-1.11	t	NMR6	Propionate
1.11-1.16	d	NMR7	Isopropanol
1.17-1.20	t	NMR8	Ethanol
1.22-1.29	q	NMR9	X5
1.30-1.34	d+q	NMR10	X6
1.35-1.38	d	NMR11	Acetoin
1.39-1.43	d	NMR12	Lactate/2-Phenylpropionate
1.48-1.53	s+t	NMR13	X7
	-	NMR14,NMR15	X8, X9
1.77-1.81	q	NMR16	6-Acetylglucose
1.97-2.00	s	NMR17	Acetamide
2.02-2.12	s	NMR18	Acetic Acid
2.12-2.14	s/d	NMR19	X10
2.13-2.16	s/d	NMR20	X11
2.16-2.19	s	NMR21	Acetoin
2.21-2.25	s+d	NMR22	Acetone
	dd	NMR23	Acetone
2.28-2.30	s	NMR24	Acetoacetate,Acetylsalicylate
2.32-2.34	d	NMR25	X12
2.37-2.40	s+t	NMR26	Malate, Glutarate, N-Acetylglutamate...
2.59-2.62	t	NMR27	Beta-Alanine, Succinate...
2.64-2.67	s	NMR28	Succinic Acid
2.81-2.85	d	NMR29	X13
2.96-3.01	d	NMR30	X14
3.18-3.21	s	NMR31	Acetylcholine
3.22-3.31	m	NMR32	Glucose
3.30-3.36	d	NMR33	Methanol
3.37-3.51	m+m	NMR34	Glucose
3.51-3.58	m	NMR35	Glucose

3.57-3.65	d	NMR36	Glucose+Fructose
3.63-3.67	q	NMR37	Ethanol
3.67-3.74	m	NMR38	Fructose+Glucose
3.74-3.78	dd	NMR39	Glucose
3.78-3.84	m	NMR40	Fructose
3.84-3.86	d	NMR41	X15
3.87-3.91	dd	NMR42	Fructose+Glucose
3.98-4.03	d+s	NMR43	Fructose
4.09-4.12	t	NMR44	Fructose
4.11-4.15	q	NMR45	X17
4.51-4.54	d+s	NMR46	X20
4.56-4.60	d	NMR47	X21
4.62-4.68	d	NMR48	Glucose
4.68-4.71	s	NMR49,NMR50,NMR51	5-HMF
5.21-5.26	d	NMR52	Glucose
5.35-5.39	d	NMR53	X22
	-	NMR54	X23
6.67-6.70	d	NMR55	X24
	-	NMR56	X25
7.52-7.55	d	NMR57	X26
8.25-8.28	s	NMR58, NMR59	Formic Acid
9.43-9.47	s	NMR60, NMR61	5-HMF
9.65-9.68	q	NMR62	X27

* Peak multiplicities: s, singlet; d, doublet; t, triplet; dd, doublet of doublets; q, quadruplet; m, multiplet.

Table 4

Table 4. Classification results for each individual data block.

DATA	CLASSIFICATION METHOD	PRETREATMENT	LV ^a	% CORRECTED CLASSIFIED					
				Train ^b			Test ^b		
				C	J	M	C	J	M
MIR+NIR	PLS-DA	Block Scaling + Mean Centering	10	90.0	85.0	79.2	100	87.5	62.5
EEM	NPLS-DA	Mean centering	12	66.7	95.0	75.0	50.0	100	83.3
¹ H-NMR peak areas	PLS-DA	Autoscaling	7	100	97.5	91.7	100	75.0	75.0

^a LVs number determined on the basis of minimum classification error in CV (Venetian blind 7 splits, keeping replicates in the same set). ^b Independent train and test sets, average correct classification rate for 5 random training/ test splitting is reported.

Table 5

Table 5. PLS-DA RESULTS OBTAINED BY MID-LEVEL FUSED DATASET WITH TWO DIFFERENT SCALING PROCEDURES

DATASET	CLASSIFICATION METHOD	PRETREATMENT	LVs ^a	% CORRECTED CLASSIFIED					
				Train ^b			Test ^b		
				C	J	M	C	J	M
Mid-Level Data Fusion	PLSDA	Autoscaling	6	100	100	91.7	100	100	100
		Block-Autoscaling	7	100	97.5	91.7	100	100	100
P-Comdim Raw		Autoscaling	2	90.0	97.5	75.0	50.0	75.0	75.0
P-Comdim Extracted Features		Autoscaling	2	96.7	100	87.5	91.7	87.5	87.5

^a LVs number determined on the basis of minimum RMSECV with Venetian blind cross validation (7 splits, 2 samples per split). ^b Independent test set, average correct classification rate for 5 random training/ test splitting is reported.

Table 6

Table 6. Salient variables for discrimination for each PDO category according to PLS-DA VIP values, which were concordant in both DF PLS-DA models, i.e. autoscaling and block-autoscaling. In parenthesis, the sign of the corresponding regression coefficients is reported.

PDOs	NIR-MIR	¹H-NMR	EEM
“Vinagre de Condado de Huelva”	PC2(+), PC3(-), PC5(+), PC8 (+)	NMR7(-), NMR11(-), NMR16(+), NMR17(+), NMR18(+), NMR24(-), NMR26(-), NMR27(+), NMR29(+), NMR30(+), NMR31(-)	F1(-), F4(+), F5(+)
“Vinagre de Jerez”	PC1(-), PC2(-), PC3(+), PC4(-), PC7(-), PC8(-)	NMR14(+), NMR16(-), NMR26(+), NMR27(-), NMR29(-), NMR31(+), NMR59(-)	F1(-), F4(-), F5(+)
“Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles”	PC1(+), PC5(-), PC8(-)	NMR16(-), NMR26(-), NMR27(-), NMR32(+), NMR35(+), NMR36(+), NMR39(+), NMR44(+), NMR48(+), NMR49(+), NMR51(+), NMR59(+), NMR61(+)	F1(+), F5(-)

Figure 1
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Figure 2
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Figure 3
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A) AUTOSCALING

B) BLOCK-AUTOSCALING

Figure 4
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A) Saliences P-ComDim raw data

Table 1: MIR, Table 2: NIR, Table 3: EEM, Table 4: NMR

B) Saliences ComDim Extracted Features

Table 1: MIR+NIR PCA scores, Table 2: PARAFAC scores EEM, Table 3: MCR components NMR

Figure 5
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Figure 6
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